

Exploring Pre-service Informatics Teachers' Ability to Assess Their Own Performance in Supporting Learners Through Algorithmic Problem Solving Processes

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Abstract

This pilot study explores N = 4 pre-service informatics teachers who were video-recorded when guiding a group of learners in solving algorithmic problem-solving tasks. Before and after the process, they were asked to assess their ability to guide the learners in a real, accepting and emphatic way when addressing and formulating questions or giving feedback. The group of learners also evaluated the competencies of their learning guides.

Keywords

Video-Vignettes, Empathy, Algorithmic Problem-Solving

1. Introduction

The skill to solve problems of algorithmic tasks depends on the amount and quality of knowledge in a domain [1] - in this case in informatics/algorithmic thinking. Educating future teachers in informatics addresses the acquisition of algorithmic skills in a problem-based context. The teaching methods need to be aligned with intended learning outcomes [2]. In accordance with the features of instructional quality, classroom management, structuring of the learning context as well as cognitive activation and student-centeredness impacts learning [3]. In accordance with the student-centered approach, students acquire their intended learning outcomes in a supportive atmosphere which is influenced by the teacher's ability to be authenticity, unconditional positive regard and empathic understanding [4].

1.1. Video Vignettes

Pre-service informatics teachers' professional vision - the ability to notice and interpret various classroom settings via video - has been well examined in particular in the educational context [5, 6, 7, 8]; in particular the following features of instructional quality as 1) *making the learning*

Informatics in Schools. A step beyond digital education. 15th International Conference on Informatics in Schools: Situation, Evolution, and Perspectives, ISSEP 2022, Vienna, Austria, September 26–28, 2022

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goals transparent to the learners, 2) activating the learners, 3) supporting and guiding the learning-processes as well as 4) evaluating it [8]. Previous studies investigated pre-service informatics teachers' perception of empathy in feedback settings where they support learners in their learning processes [9]. Vignettes enable a standardized assessment using videos in different classroom settings [10]. It is applied in education research with becoming teacher [11, 12].

The goal of this explorative pilot-study is to further develop a video-vignette instrument as a professional reflection tool for informatics students to reflect and further develop their ability to guide learning processes in the context of algorithmic thinking in a student-centered way. The following research question is driving this study: *To what extent can the pre-service informatics teachers assess their performance to guide learners in a student-centered way?*

2. Method

The sample consists of $N = 4$ (1 female and 3 male at the average age of 25) pre-service computer science teachers. They participate in a didactics seminar in informatics. During the semester they run workshops with pupils and are videotaped. During the semester, they reflect their teaching competencies based on the video recordings from them. For this experiment they were trained to guide learners in student-centered teaching (authenticity, unconditional positive regard and empathy) way in accordance with [4]. The pre-service teachers each chose an algorithmic task they wanted to use in a student-centered way. The task for the learning group included problem-oriented tasks where they had to work together to find an algorithm to solve a problem. The tasks were based on algorithms in [13]. Fig. 1 shows an example of an algorithmic task where students were asked to develop an algorithm to search for an object in a sorted CD collection and describe it in natural language.

Figure 1: Example of an task on searching a CD in a sorted collection: "Describe an algorithm in natural language to find the selected CD" [13]

Before each setting of guiding the group of learners in their algorithmic problem-solving tasks, they were asked to predict their degree of student-centeredness before guiding the group of learners and estimating their student-centeredness afterwards on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = not at all true, 2 = rather not true, 3 = neither false nor true, 4 = rather true, 5 = totally true). We used an instrument, we developed and piloted before with $N = 20$ pre-service teachers in informatics [9].

2.1. Reliability

The instrument showed a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.94 [9]. We further shortened it, deleting 6 items which had an internal consistency of less than 0.62 and reformulating 2 items. Another item was deleted due to similarity. In this study, the assessment instrument consisted of 18 items. The scales realness and acceptance consisted of 2 items each and the empathy scale consisted of 14 items. Empathy included the subscales response behaviour, accuracy of assessment and atmosphere. The scales are based on instruments which were developed in the therapeutic context [14, 15, 16], in educational context [17] as well as in computer science education [18, 19].

3. Preliminary Results and Discussion

This section shows the preliminary findings of our empirical study that aimed: (1) to further develop a vignette-instrument on teacher's professionalization and (2) to assess pre-service teachers' ability and perception of student-centeredness when put into concrete settings where they guide learning processes in algorithmic thinking. First insights are shown in Table 1. The pre-service informatics teachers underestimated their ability to guide learners in a real, accepting and emphatic way. Further results will be discussed in the poster presentation.

Table 1

Description of the self-estimation regarding student-centeredness before and after

Algorithmic Task	Realness		Acceptance		Empathy	
	AM	SD	AM	SD	AM	SD
self-estimation before guiding a group of learners	4.13	0.48	4.13	0.75	3.63	0.62
self-estimation after guiding a group of learners	4.25	0.65	4.38	0.48	3.68	0.24

Therefore, this explorative case study gives first insights into pre-service teachers in informatics have difficulties in accurately predicting their expected performance when guiding learners in problem-solving tasks of algorithmic thinking. In a next step, further examples will be videotaped and assessed and N = 30 informatic students will be asked to rate the different settings with regard to student-centeredness as well.

4. Conclusion

Professionalizing future informatics teachers in guiding learners through the learning processes of solving algorithmic task in a problem-based context is a central issue in teacher education in informatics. This vignette-instrument investigates the reflection as well as professionalization. However, this study is limited in various points which must be addressed in future work. The sample includes only a very limited amount of pre-service teachers in informatics. In future work, more learners will be included who will be videotaped when guiding learners in problem-based algorithmic thinking tasks. Future work needs to include more videos as well as more students to rate the vignettes and thus use this instrument for reflection.

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